

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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XALQARO RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYANING O'ZBEKISTON AN'ANAVIY BANKLARNING RAQOBAT MUHITIGA TA'SIRI

UO'K 330.332 Raqamli iqtisodiyot.

Abdujabbarov Abdurasul Abdurashid o'g'li

Aksiyadorlik tijorat banki "Biznesni rivojlantirish banki" Raqamli biznes departamenti yetakchi menejeri, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda xalqaro raqobat sharoitida an'anaviy banklarning muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishi va raqamli integratsiya orqali raqobatga qarshi kurashish borasidagi sa'y-harakatlari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Maqolada O'zbekistondagi an'anaviy banklar raqamli texnologiyalardan qanday foydalanayotgani va raqamli texnologiyalar orqali daromadlarini oshirayotgani ko'rib chiqiladi va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya kontekstida tartibga solish masalalari haqida tushuncha beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli iqtisodiyot, bank sektori, an'anaviy banklar, fintech kompaniyalari, raqamli integratsiya, mijozlar tajribasi, mobil banking, onlayn banking, raqamli to'lovlar, yangi texnologiyalar, Hukumat tashabbuslari, normativ-huquqiy baza, naqd pulsiz to'lov tizimlari, raqamli ko'nikmalar, hamkorliklar, sotib olishlar, IT infratuzilmasi, ma'lumotlar tahlili, sun'iy intellekt, texnologiya, Mijozlarga e'tibor, operatsion samaradorlik, raqobat, xalqaro muvofiqlik, qiyinchiliklar, imkoniyatlar, global hamkorlik.

Abstract: This article provides information on the successful development of Uzbekistan's traditional banks amid international competition and their efforts to strengthen themselves against competition through integration. It discusses how traditional banks in Uzbekistan are leveraging their development and enhancing their income through competition, as well as providing insights into regulatory and legal issues in the context of international digital integration.

Key words: Digital economy, banking sector, traditional banks, fintech companies, digital integration, customer experience, mobile banking, online banking, digital payment, emerging technologies, government initiatives, regulatory framework, cashless payment system, digital skills, partnerships, acquisitions, IT infrastructure, data analytics, artificial intelligence, blockchain technology, customer focus, operational efficiency, compliance, financial inclusion, competition, international compliance, challenges, opportunities, global collaboration.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация об успешном развитии традиционных банков Узбекистана в условиях международной конкуренции и их усилиях по противостоянию конкуренции путем интеграции. В статье рассматривается, как традиционные банки Узбекистана используют преимущества своего развития и повышают свои доходы за счет конкуренции, а также дается представление о нормативно-правовых вопросах в контексте международной цифровой интеграции.

Ключевые слова: Цифровая экономика, банковский сектор, традиционные банки, финтех-компании, цифровая интеграция, клиентский опыт, мобильный банкинг, онлайн-банкинг, цифровые платежи, новые технологии, государственные инициативы, нормативная база, безналичные платежные системы, цифровые навыки, партнерства, приобретения, ИТ-инфраструктура, аналитика данных, искусственный интеллект, технология блокчейн, клиентоориентированность, операционная эффективность, соответствие требованиям, финансовая доступность, конкуренция, международное соответствие, вызовы, возможности, глобальное сотрудничество.

INTRODUCTION

"Without a digital economy, the country's economy has no future."
Shavkat Mirziyoyev

Amidst the vast plains of central Asia, Uzbekistan stands at a pivotal juncture. Its once Agriculture and industry-driven economy now finds itself on the cusp of a digital revolution, fueled by the relentless tide of global connectivity. At the forefront of this transformation lies the banking sector, where established institutions face an existential challenge: adapt or be swept away by the digital tsunami of international digital integration.

- **Blockchain Technology:** Blockchain technology holds the potential for secure and transparent financial transactions, potentially revolutionizing areas like cross-border payments and trade finance.
- **Big Data Analytics:** Utilizing customer data through analytics tools enables banks to gain valuable insights into customer behavior, allowing for personalized financial products and targeted marketing campaigns.

Government Initiatives. The Uzbek government actively supports digitalization initiatives in the banking sector.

- **Promoting Financial Inclusion:** Government programs aim to increase internet and mobile phone penetration, particularly in rural areas, making digital banking services more accessible to a wider population.
- **Regulatory Framework:** The central Bank of Uzbekistan is establishing regulations that facilitate the adoption of digital technologies while ensuring consumer protection and financial stability.

1. Strategy for the Development of the Cashless Payment System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2025.

This strategy aims to increase the share of cashless payments in the economy, develop the cashless payment infrastructure, and make cashless payments more accessible to the population.

2. Concept for the Development of the Digital Economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

This concept focuses on creating favorable conditions for the growth of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, integrating digital technologies into all economic sectors, and improving the quality of life for citizens.

3. Roadmap for the Development of the Payment System of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025.

This roadmap outlines the modernization of Uzbekistan's payment system, the implementation of new technologies, and the enhancement of the payment market's competitiveness.

4. Regulation on the Procedure for Making Payments Using Payment Cards.

This regulation governs the procedures for using payment cards for transactions within Uzbekistan.

EMBRACING TRANSFORMATION: THE IMPERATIVE FOR SURVIVAL

For traditional banks in Uzbekistan, survival is not a mere aspiration; it is an imperative. Navigating the treacherous waters of the digital age demands a transformative leap, shedding their antiquated structures and emerging as agile, innovative players within the globalized digital ecosystem.

Investing in Infrastructure. Banks are upgrading their IT infrastructure to support digital platforms and integrate them seamlessly with existing systems.

Developing Digital Skills. Training programs are being implemented to equip bank employees with the necessary skills and knowledge to operate effectively in the digital environment.

- **Partnerships and Acquisitions:** Some banks for example Kapitalbank and Uzum Xalqbanki with Paynet are partnering with FinTech companies or acquiring smaller digital players to gain access to cutting-edge technologies and expertise.

This digital transformation journey is still ongoing, but it's evident that traditional banks in Uzbekistan are embracing the opportunities presented by international digital integration to enhance customer experience, improve operational efficiency, and compete in the evolving financial landscape.

THIS TRANSFORMATION NECESSITATES A MULTIFACETED APPROACH

Modernizing IT infrastructure is paramount. Replacing outdated systems with cloud-based solutions empowers real-time data processing and facilitates seamless digital transactions.

- **Digital Skills Development:** Equipping employees with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in a digital environment is crucial. Training in data analytics, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity becomes essential.
- **Fostering Innovation and collaboration:** cultivating a culture of innovation, where experimentation and calculated risk-taking are encouraged, is vital. collaborations with FinTech companies and other technology partners unlock access to cutting-edge solutions.
- **The UZUM ecosystem is an example of this customer centricity at the core:** Prioritizing the customer must be the cornerstone of operations. Designing products and services tailored to individual needs and preferences, while ensuring seamless and convenient experiences across all digital channels, becomes paramount. State bank reform remains a priority and should focus on improving governance, achieving commercial objectives, and preparing them for privatization. SBs dominate the financial system with 68 percent of bank assets at end-2023. After the privatization of Ipoteka bank,

the authorities have continued to make important progress by slating two large state banks (Asaka and SQB) for privatization. Going forward, further accelerating privatization of the SBs would improve competition, level the playing field, allow more efficient allocation of resources, and increase access to financial services. Banks that remain state owned should be mandated to operate commercially with efficient systems and appropriate governance structures

THE FUTURE OF BANKING: A SYMBIOTIC PARTNERSHIP

The digital revolution is not a harbinger of the demise of traditional banks; it is a catalyst for their transformation. The future holds the promise of a symbiotic relationship between traditional banks and FinTech companies, each leveraging their respective strengths to create a more inclusive, efficient, and innovative financial ecosystem.

Traditional banks, with their established brand reputation, loyal customer base, and regulatory expertise, provide the stability and trust that customers value. FinTech companies, with their agility, disruptive innovation, and customer-centric approach, bring fresh ideas, cutting-edge technologies, and unparalleled user experiences to the table.

By forging strategic partnerships, traditional banks and FinTech companies can harness the power of the digital tsunami of international integration to create a future of banking that is more prosperous, inclusive, and empowering for all Uzbeks.

Outdated Infrastructure. Many banks still rely on outdated IT infrastructure that is not designed to handle the demands of modern digital platforms. This hinders their ability to integrate seamlessly with new technologies, leading to inefficiencies and limitations in service offerings.

Integration Difficulties. Integrating legacy systems with new digital platforms can be complex and expensive, requiring significant investment and expertise. This can slow down the digital transformation process and hinder the adoption of innovative solutions.

Evolving Regulatory Landscape. The regulatory framework governing digital banking is constantly evolving, requiring banks to adapt their operations and compliance procedures to meet new standards. This can be a complex and time-consuming process, especially for smaller banks with limited resources.

International compliance. Complying with international regulations like Know your customer (Kyc) and Anti-Money Laundering (AML) can be challenging, particularly for banks with limited experience operating in a globalized environment.

COMPETITION FROM FINTECH COMPANIES

FinTech companies are known for their agility and ability to quickly develop and launch innovative financial products and services. This can make it difficult for traditional banks to keep pace and compete effectively.

Customer Focus. FinTech companies like Click and Payme often prioritize customer experience and convenience, offering user-friendly interfaces and streamlined processes that can attract customers away from traditional banks. Has taken over the P2P market

Disruptive Technologies. FinTech companies are at the forefront of adopting disruptive technologies like blockchain and artificial intelligence, potentially revolutionizing financial services and creating new challenges for traditional banks. MNGUZ - First uzbek criptoblockchain project can be an example of this.

These challenges can significantly hinder the digital transformation efforts of traditional banks in Uzbekistan. To thrive in this dynamic environment, banks need to prioritize modernizing their infrastructure, and IABS (integrated automated banking system) FIDO with monopolized crm systems should go out of business. 55% of Uzbek banks work in this system. Navigating the evolving regulatory landscape, and finding ways to compete effectively with agile FinTech players.

OPPORTUNITIES ARISING FROM DIGITAL INTEGRATION

International digital integration presents a plethora of opportunities for traditional banks in Uzbekistan:

Expanding customer Reach. Overcoming Geographical Limitations: Digital platforms enable banks to reach customers beyond the physical limitations of branch networks. This opens doors to new customer segments across the country and potentially even beyond Uzbekistan's borders, significantly expanding their market reach.

Example: Kaspi.kz

Kaspi.kz, a leading digital bank in Kazakhstan, exemplifies this transformation. Through its innovative mobile app and online platform, Kaspi has revolutionized the banking landscape by providing convenient and accessible financial services to a vast customer base across Kazakhstan.

Multilingual Support: Catering to a diverse customer base, Kaspi offers its services in multiple languages, further enhancing accessibility.

By embracing digital integration, Kaspi has become a dominant force in the Kazakhstani banking sector, demonstrating the immense potential of digital platforms in expanding customer reach and overcoming geographical limitations.

Financial Inclusion: By offering digital financial services through mobile apps and online platforms, banks can reach previously unbanked populations, particularly in rural areas, promoting financial inclusion and driving economic growth.

Improving Operational Efficiency. Automation: Digitalization allows for the automation of repetitive tasks like account management, loan processing, and customer service inquiries. This frees up bank employees to focus on more complex tasks and value-added services, leading to increased efficiency and cost savings.

Data-Driven Decision-Making. Digital platforms generate vast amounts of customer data. Utilizing analytics tools to analyze this data enables banks to gain deeper insights into customer behavior, allowing for more informed decision-making, targeted marketing campaigns, and the development of personalized financial products.

Streamlined Processes. Digitalization facilitates the streamlining of internal processes, reducing manual work and paperwork, leading to faster transaction processing and improved service delivery.

ENHANCING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE

Convenience and Accessibility. Digital platforms offer 24/7 access to financial services, allowing customers to manage their finances anytime and anywhere. This convenience and accessibility significantly enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Personalization: Utilizing customer data, banks can personalize financial products and services to meet individual needs and preferences, creating a more tailored and engaging customer experience.

Innovation: Digital integration opens doors to the adoption of innovative technologies like AI-powered identification system MYID uzinfocom, chatbots and virtual assistants, providing 24/7 customer support and offering a more interactive and user-friendly experience.

By embracing these opportunities, traditional banks in Uzbekistan can leverage the power of international digital integration to expand their reach, optimize operations, and deliver a superior customer experience, solidifying their position in the evolving financial landscape.

IMPACT ON THE COMPETITIVE LANDSCAPE

International digital integration is fundamentally reshaping the competitive dynamics among traditional banks in Uzbekistan.

Increased competition: New Entrants: Digital integration lowers barriers to entry, allowing FinTech companies and foreign banks with strong digital capabilities to compete with established players. This intensifies competition in the market, forcing traditional banks to innovate and adapt to retain their market share.

Shifting customer Preferences: As customer expectations shift towards digital convenience and personalized financial services, banks that fail to keep pace with digitalization risk losing customers to competitors who offer more advanced and user-friendly digital solutions. TBC first Digital bank in Uzbekistan from Georgia can be an example of this.

Strategies for Staying competitive. Traditional banks in Uzbekistan are employing various strategies to stay competitive in the digital era. Banks are actively investing in upgrading their IT infrastructure, developing digital platforms, and adopting innovative technologies to offer a wider range of digital financial services.

Partnerships and Acquisitions: collaborating with FinTech companies or acquiring smaller digital players allows traditional banks to gain access to cutting-edge technologies and expertise, accelerating their digital transformation journey.

Focus on customer Experience: Prioritizing user-friendly interfaces, personalized financial solutions, and seamless customer service across digital channels is crucial to attracting and retaining customers in the digital age.

Data-Driven Strategies: Utilizing customer data analytics to understand customer behavior and preferences enables banks to develop targeted marketing campaigns, personalize financial products, and optimize service delivery.

Differentiation through Existing Strengths. Established banks often have a strong brand reputation and customer loyalty built over decades. Leveraging this trust alongside digital innovation can be a powerful strategy.

Physical Branch Network: While not a substitute for digital offerings, existing branch networks can still provide valuable touchpoints for customers who prefer in-person interactions or require assistance with complex financial matters.

By embracing digital transformation, prioritizing customer experience, and effectively leveraging their existing strengths, traditional banks in Uzbekistan can remain competitive in the dynamic landscape reshaped by international digital integration.

REGULATORY ENVIRONMENT AND COMPLIANCE

The regulatory framework governing digital banking in Uzbekistan is still evolving, but several key aspects are crucial for traditional banks to understand

Central Bank's Role

The central Bank of Uzbekistan (cBU) plays a central role in regulating digital banking activities. They issue regulations and guidelines for:

- consumer protection: Ensuring customer data privacy, security, and fair treatment in the digital environment.

Anti-money laundering (AML) and Know your customer (Kyc) compliance: Preventing financial crimes and ensuring proper customer identification and verification procedures.

- cybersecurity: Establishing standards for secure digital platforms and data protection measures.

Operational requirements: Defining specific regulations for digital banking services like mobile payments and online account management.

- compliance with International Standards

As Uzbekistan integrates with the global financial ecosystem, compliance with international standards becomes increasingly important

Financial Action Task Force (FATF) Recommendations: Uzbekistan is a member of the FATF, which sets international standards for combating money laundering and terrorist financing. compliance with these recommendations is crucial for preventing financial crime and maintaining international trust.

Basel committee Standards: The Basel committee on Banking Supervision sets global standards for capital adequacy, risk management, and corporate governance. Adherence to these standards helps ensure financial stability and sound banking practices in the digital era.

For traditional banks in Uzbekistan, adhering to the regulatory framework and international standards is critical for several reasons:

Maintaining Operational Legitimacy. Operating within the legal boundaries set by regulators ensures that banks can conduct their digital banking activities legally and avoid potential sanctions.

Building customer Trust: Demonstrating compliance with data privacy and security regulations fosters customer trust and confidence in the digital banking system.

Facilitating International cooperation. compliance with international standards allows Uzbek banks to participate in global financial markets and collaborate with international partners.

By staying updated on evolving regulations and proactively implementing compliance measures, traditional banks can navigate the digital landscape effectively and maintain a secure and trustworthy environment for their digital banking operations.

CASE STUDIES OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN UZBEK BANKS.

(Qishloq Qurilish Bank) Biznesni Rivojlantirish Bank's Digital Transformation.

Transformation: Formerly known as Qishloq Qurilish Bank, the Biznesni Rivojlantirish Banki (BRB) underwent a significant digital metamorphosis. with PwC

Shedding the Past: BRB embraced cutting-edge technologies, leaving behind outdated infrastructure and practices.

Data-Driven Approach: Utilizing data analytics, BRB tailors its services to Uzbekistan's evolving needs.

Empowering Entrepreneurs: BRB supports entrepreneurs, business through financing, mentorship, and networking opportunities.

Financial Inclusion: BRB leverages digital platforms QUANT to provide financial services to all Uzbeks.

- collaboration: BRB partners with FinTech companies Intend, Payme and others to amplify its impact.

Shaping the Future: BRB actively contributes to Uzbekistan's digital leadership and economic prosperity.

Sanoat Qurilish bank

Reaching micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises with digital banking. Building on its competitive advantages, Uzprom actively used digital banking channels since the beginning of the pandemic in 2020 for

better outreach to MSMEs, especially in rural areas. Uzprom was one of the first SOBs to adopt a digitalization strategy, including introducing digital channels. Uzprom increased the percentage of customers using digital banking tools to 47% and aims to further expand the share of digital channels in 2018–2023. Uzprom has also been improving its IT structure to achieve operational efficiencies by automating business processes.

Ipak yuli Bank

Challenge: Legacy IT infrastructure hindering the development of modern digital platforms.

Solution: Partnered with Adastra Business consulting to develop a comprehensive IT strategy. This involved optimizing internal processes, automating tasks, and improving IT architecture.

Outcome: Improved operational efficiency, streamlined service delivery, and a foundation for further digital initiatives.

Asaka Bank

Challenge: Expanding customer reach beyond physical branches.

Solution: Launched a user-friendly mobile banking app offering account management, bill payments, and loan applications.

Outcome: Increased customer adoption of digital services, reaching new customer segments beyond branch locations.

Aloqa Bank

Challenge: Enhancing customer experience and personalization.

Solution: Implemented AI-powered chatbots on their online platform for 24/7 customer support and personalized financial recommendations based on customer data analysis.

Outcome: Improved customer satisfaction through readily available support and tailored financial solutions.

Turon Bank

Challenge: competing with FinTech agility and innovation.

Solution: Partnered with a FinTech startup specializing in mobile payments, integrating their technology to offer a seamless mobile wallet service.

Outcome: Gained access to cutting-edge technology and expanded their digital service offerings, remaining competitive in the evolving landscape.

These are just a few examples, and the digital transformation journey is ongoing for many Uzbek banks. By studying these case studies, traditional banks can gain valuable insights into:

Overcoming specific challenges: Understanding how other banks have addressed similar obstacles can provide valuable strategies and best practices.

Leveraging innovative solutions: Learning from successful implementations of AI, mobile banking, and partnerships can inspire further innovation within their institutions.

Adapting to the changing landscape: Recognizing the diverse approaches taken by other banks highlights the need for flexibility and continuous adaptation in the digital era.

FUTURE OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSION

The prospects for traditional banks in Uzbekistan within the context of international digital integration are both challenging and promising.

Challenges and Uncertainties. The continuous evolution of digital technologies like AI and blockchain will require constant adaptation and investment from traditional banks.

Navigating the evolving regulatory framework and ensuring compliance with international standards will remain an ongoing challenge.

- competition: The threat of FinTech companies and foreign banks with advanced digital capabilities will intensify, requiring traditional banks to continuously innovate and differentiate themselves.

RIDING THE DIGITAL WAVE: A CALL TO ACTION

The digital tsunami is not a threat, but an opportunity. For traditional banks in Uzbekistan, it presents a chance to reinvent themselves, to become more relevant, competitive, and impactful in the lives of their customers.

The time for action is now. The future of banking in Uzbekistan hangs in the balance. By embracing digital transformation, traditional banks can not only survive but thrive, riding the crest of the digital wave to a brighter and more prosperous future.

Digital integration has the potential to significantly drive financial inclusion by reaching previously unbanked populations, particularly in rural areas.

Improved Efficiency and Growth. By embracing digitalization, banks can optimize operations, reduce costs, and expand their customer base, leading to potential economic growth.

Global collaboration: International digital integration opens doors for collaboration with international partners and participation in global financial markets.

CONCLUSION

In this dynamic environment, the future of traditional banks in Uzbekistan hinges on their ability to:

Embrace Digital Transformation: continuously invest in modernizing infrastructure, adopting innovative technologies, and developing user-friendly digital platforms.

Prioritize customer Experience. Offer personalized financial solutions, seamless digital services, and readily available customer support.

Maintain Regulatory compliance. Proactively adhere to evolving regulations and international standards to ensure operational legitimacy and customer trust.

Leverage Existing Strengths. combine their brand reputation, physical branch network, and customer base with digital innovation to create a unique competitive advantage.

By successfully navigating these challenges and seizing the opportunities presented by international digital integration, traditional banks in Uzbekistan can not only survive but also thrive in the evolving landscape of the banking sector, playing a crucial role in driving financial inclusion and economic growth within the country.

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